

Detection of faint galaxies with GAIA

L. Lindegren (25 February 2000)

SAG-LL-29

1 Introduction

The capability of GAIA to detect faint galaxies is investigated by means of HST/WFPC2 images, which have a resolution and pixel size which are not too different from GAIA's ASM1 detector. A suitable database is the Medium Deep Survey (MDS; Ratnatunga et al., AJ 118, 86, 1999), which contains several hundred random fields distributed over the whole sky. Images were usually taken in two colour bands (F606W and F814W) and are sufficiently deep that they can be considered noiseless in comparison with ASM1 data. The MDS project provides, via <http://archive.stsci.edu/mds/>, stacked and calibrated images, as well as catalogues of all detected objects (stars and galaxies) down to $I \simeq 23$.

From this database I extracted images of the brightest galaxies in a number of fields at high galactic latitudes. The images were photometrically transformed to the GAIA (G) system, converted to expected photoelectron counts, resampled to the ASM1 sample size, after which the theoretical detectability of the image was assessed in terms of its total signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). The cumulative distribution of SNR could thus be established, from which the total number of theoretically detectable galaxies is estimated.

2 Detectability of general structures

From the known brightness distribution and detector characteristics, it is possible to determine whether a general structure (such as a galaxy) is *in principle* detectable or not, without specifying the actual detection algorithm. This is based on the assumption that no detection algorithm can be more efficient than an optimally matched filter. The output from such a filter has a SNR whose expected value R can be computed directly from the noise characteristics and the expected image:

$$R = \left[\sum_i \frac{e_i^2}{e_i + b + r^2} \right]^{1/2}. \quad (1)$$

Here e_i is the expected number of photoelectrons in sample i from the structure (i.e. excluding background); b is the sky background in electrons per sample and r the rms readout noise (RON) per sample. [The corresponding matched filter is $e_i/(e_i + b + r^2)$.] In the absence of background and readout noise we have simply $R = \sqrt{E}$, as expected, where $E = \sum_i e_i$ is the total number of photoelectrons in the structure. When the background or RON dominates, the SNR is essentially proportional to $(\sum_i e_i^2)^{1/2}$. It is useful to characterise the structure by means of a quantity which I call the *concentration index*,

$$\gamma = \sum_i (e_i/E)^2. \quad (2)$$

If all the light is concentrated in a single sample, then $\gamma = 1$. If the light is evenly spread out over n samples, then $\gamma = 1/n$. Thus γ^{-1} can be regarded as the effective number of samples over which the structure is spread. The limiting expressions for the SNR are:

$$R \simeq \begin{cases} E^{1/2} & \text{(bright structures)} \\ E \left[\frac{\gamma}{b+r^2} \right]^{1/2} & \text{(faint structures)} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

However, in the general case one must use Eq. (1).

We know that point-like sources are detected quite successfully by ASM1 down to $G \simeq 20.5$ ($E \simeq 217$). With the effective PSF of ASM1 (SAG-LL-025) and $r = 10.9$ this magnitude gives $R \simeq 7$. (The sky level at 22 mag arcsec⁻² is $b \simeq 0.9$, which can be neglected compared with r^2 .) Theoretically, a somewhat lower detection threshold could perhaps be used without too many false detections. In the following I will assume $R_{\min} = 5$, which approximately corresponds to $G = 21.0$ for point objects. The same limit should then ideally apply also to extended objects, i.e. a galaxy could be detected if $R > R_{\min}$. By means of Eq. (1) we can thus easily determine the detectability of arbitrary structures $\{e_i\}$. From the HST images we can get a rough estimate of the photoelectron counts for faint galaxies. For this we must however consider the photometric transformation to the G band, the different pixel sizes of WFPC2 and GAIA, and the different PSFs.

3 Transformation from WFPC2 filters to G

The calibrated WFPC2 images give intensities expressed in data numbers (DN or ADU). Let DN be the integrated data number for an object (after sky subtraction). DN is converted to an equivalent absolute flux density (at the effective wavelength of the filter) through

$$f_\lambda = \text{PHOTFLAM} \times \text{DN}/\text{EXPTIME} \quad [\text{erg s}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ \AA}^{-1}], \quad (4)$$

where PHOTFLAM is constant for a given camera/filter combination (see the HST Handbook, Table 28.1) and EXPTIME is the exposure time in seconds (taken from the FITS header). Magnitudes in the STMAG system then follow from

$$m_{\text{ST}} = -21.10 - 2.5 \log f_\lambda. \quad (5)$$

Images taken with filters F606W and F814W result in magnitudes $m_{\text{ST}}(\text{F606W})$ and $m_{\text{ST}}(\text{F814W})$ from which a colour index can be computed:

$$C = m_{\text{ST}}(\text{F606W}) - m_{\text{ST}}(\text{F814W}). \quad (6)$$

We want to estimate the number of photoelectrons (E) produced in ASM1 of GAIA as function of these magnitudes. The G magnitude is defined in Section 6.3.2 of the GAIA Report (V1.5). Using the Gunn & Stryker spectral atlas, the following relation was found to be accurate within ± 0.1 mag (Fig. 3):

$$G = m_{\text{ST}}(\text{F814W}) + 0.035 + 0.800C - 0.420C^2 + 0.1353C^3 - 0.0187C^4. \quad (7)$$

Although this transformation was determined from unreddened stellar spectra (with $-1.3 \leq C \leq +3.8$), I assume that it holds also for the composite spectra of galaxies. The number of electrons in ASM1 (with integration time 0.86 s) is:

$$E = 3.44 \times 10^{10-0.4G}. \quad (8)$$

FIGURE 1. Relation between synthetic WFPC2 magnitudes $m_{ST}(F606W)$ and $m_{ST}(F814W)$ and the GAIA magnitude G , using 175 stellar spectra from Gunn & Stryker (circles). The curve is the fitted Eq. (7).

Since the F606W and F814W images match approximately pixel-by-pixel, the above transformation could in principle be applied to each pixel, producing an equivalent ‘GAIA’ image at the WFPC2 resolution. However, to reduce sensitivity to noise and pixel mismatch, I apply the transformation only to the integrated data numbers of a given structure (star or galaxy, after background subtraction) as identified in the MDS database; this gives an estimate of the total number of ASM1 electrons in the structure (E), and these are then re-distributed in proportion to the mean of the F606W and F814W structures. Before integration, bad pixels are replaced by interpolated values.

4 Pixel size and PSF

PSF here means the total PSF (optical PSF degraded by the pixel response function and, for GAIA, the TDI smearing). In image analysis it is this PSF that counts and therefore it is necessary to consider the pixel size and PSF together. Any resampling scheme (required to change the pixel size) also changes the PSF. The following basic data are assumed.

WFPC2: Only WFC images are used, for which the pixel size is very nearly 0.1×0.1 arcsec². Typical PSFs (including the pixel response function) are shown in Table 1 for a source centred on a pixel (left) and at the corner of a pixel (right). The concentration index is $\gamma = 0.13$ and 0.10 , respectively.

ASM1: The sample used in ASM1 consists of 2×2 pixels, i.e. 0.074×0.223 arcsec² (along $\times$ across scan). Typical PSFs are shown in Table 2 (centre and corner of sample). They are computed using the programmes described in SAG-LL-025, assuming $V - I \simeq 1.6$, the QE curve for CCD#1B and the typical aberrations at field point #13. The concentration index is $\gamma = 0.24$ and 0.15 , respectively.

Although the resolution of HST is in principle better than GAIA, the strong undersampling in WFC makes it practically impossible to resample the WFC images in a way that mimics both the pixel geometry and the PSF of GAIA. For estimating detectabilities, the exact pixel geometry is however not important. More relevant are the solid angle per sample (for extended sources) and the concentration index (for point sources). I therefore try to reproduce only these two parameters. The ASM1 sample area can be reproduced by resampling the WFC pixels in steps of 1.3 pixels in each coordinate. The resulting PSFs, shown in Table 3, have concentration index $\gamma = 0.16$ and 0.12 , respectively. The resampled PSFs are thus a factor 0.67–0.80 lower than in ASM1, which could lower the computed SNR by 10–20 per cent for unresolved objects.

TABLE 1. Typical PSFs (in per mille) for the WFC at $\lambda = 600$ nm, including pixel response function. Pixel size is 0.100×0.100 arcsec². γ is the concentration index of the sampled PSF. (WFPC2 Instrument Handbook, Ch. 5.5)

centre of pixel, $\gamma = 0.13$					corner of pixel, $\gamma = 0.10$				
3	7	9	6	2	7	26	26	9	3
7	41	78	41	8	30	149	156	33	5
10	86	304	94	13	22	137	163	32	4
5	28	82	35	6	6	23	29	7	2
2	5	10	6	3	2	3	3	2	2

TABLE 2. Typical PSFs for the ASM1 of GAIA ($V - I = 1.6$). Samples consist of 2×2 pixels. The sample response function and TDI smearing are included. Pixel size is 0.074×0.223 arcsec². Horizontal is along the scan. (Computed according to SAG-LL-025)

centre of sample, $\gamma = 0.24$			corner of sample, $\gamma = 0.15$			
18	133	15	1	29	25	1
53	450	47	10	209	191	10
13	104	13	10	184	179	9
			1	15	15	1

TABLE 3. The PSFs in Table 1 rebinned to a sample size of 0.13×0.13 arcsec², i.e. the same solid angle as the ASM1 sample. This is as close as one can get to simulate the PSF of GAIA/ASM1 by simple resampling of the HST/WFC images, in terms of sample area and concentration index. That the resulting sample has the wrong shape (square instead of rectangular) is less important for the detection capability.

centre of sample, $\gamma = 0.16$					corner of sample, $\gamma = 0.12$				
1	4	6	3	1	6	22	22	7	1
4	36	82	35	4	26	166	175	29	2
6	87	358	96	8	19	151	182	27	2
3	24	83	30	4	5	20	24	6	1
1	3	6	4	1	1	1	1	1	0

5 The MDS fields

20 fields at high galactic latitudes ($|b| > 50^\circ$) were selected from the MDS programme for this study. These fields are listed in Table 4.

The stacked images in F814W and F606W were photometrically transformed to the G band, and hence to expected electron counts, and resampled as described in Sects. 3 and 4. In each field the 100 brightest objects (as listed in the MLE catalogue) were analyzed within a radius of 20 samples (2.6 arcsec) around the object centre. This is large enough to estimate R accurately by means of Eq. (1), even if some of the light in the outer part of the galaxy image is missed. Cases of disturbed regions were eliminated by searching around each detected object for another object with higher SNR, in which case the fainter object was rejected (since its SNR was probably much overestimated). To study the sensitivity of the detection process to the readout noise, three different levels were assumed: $r = 10.9$, 5.0 and 2.0 electrons rms. The first value is the current assumption for ASM1.

Objects classified by the MDS team as ‘stellar’ in both filters were assumed to be stars. All other objects were assumed to be galaxies. Some of the resulting statistics are given in Table 4. (The mean density of stellar objects, 1100 resp. 1700 deg^{-2} brighter than $G = 20$ and 21, is in reasonable agreement with galaxy models (TBC), but it is of course possible that some of them are actually very compact galaxies.) Figures 2 to 5 show the three galaxies with $R > 5$ and the next one, with $R = 4.8$ just below the assumed detection threshold.

TABLE 4. The MDS fields used in this study. Each field is 4.77 arcmin^2 ; the total area is 0.0265 deg^2 . The table gives the number of stars per field brighter than $G = 20$ and 21, and the number of detectable galaxies (with $\text{SNR} \geq 5$) for an rms readout noise of 10.9, 5.0 and 2.0 e^- .

field	galactic coord.		no. of stars		no. of galaxies ($R \geq 5$)		
	ℓ	b	$G \leq 20$	$G \leq 21$	$r=10.9$	$r=5.0$	$r=2.0$
u26x1	96.35	+60.53	1	1	0	0	2
u26x2	96.35	+60.55	3	4	0	0	2
u26x3	96.35	+60.58	0	0	0	2	2
u26x4	96.35	+59.89	2	2	0	1	1
u2841	57.55	+82.06	0	1	0	0	0
u2fq2	67.70	-51.13	2	3	0	1	18
u30h3	314.51	+69.20	2	2	0	0	1
ua-01	212.90	-87.07	0	0	0	0	0
ua-30	249.13	-88.18	1	2	0	0	0
ua400	30.01	-84.10	1	2	1	1	4
uci10	138.73	-57.99	2	4	0	1	2
udm10	172.22	-51.95	1	3	1	4	4
udt00	241.12	-51.23	2	3	0	0	3
uhdf1	125.89	+54.83	1	3	1	1	3
uwy02	298.60	+51.25	2	3	0	2	4
ux100	5.87	+58.23	2	3	0	3	4
uxy10	295.05	+61.95	2	2	0	1	3
uy400	33.55	+66.62	2	2	0	1	1
uy401	34.37	+66.62	2	3	0	1	6
uz607	317.14	+84.83	1	3	0	0	0
sum			29	46	3	19	60

